

INTERNAL FRICTION IN AlCu-Al₂O₃ METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

L. Parrini and R. Schaller

Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Institut de Génie Atomique, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

In MMCs the metal matrix is exposed to plastic deformation and damage accumulation in the region close to the reinforcements, following mechanical or thermal stress. In this connection, Al-4%Cu based MMCs reinforced with 10%, 20% and 30% Al₂O₃ fibers were characterized by internal friction (IF) measurements. IF measurements as a function of the vibration amplitude exhibit a peak which has been connected with a solid friction phenomenon at metal-fiber interfaces and interface loosening. On this basis, the IF measurements allowed us to characterize damage accumulation at matrix-fiber interfaces in different composites.

INTRODUCTION

The effect of internal stresses on the mechanical behaviour of metal matrix composites (MMCs) can be considerable. These stresses arise because the reinforcement and the metal matrix can differ in such properties as the coefficient of thermal expansion [1], elastic modulus and deformation mode (i. e. reinforcements remain elastic while the matrix deforms plastically) [2]. The magnitude of these stresses can be considerable [3-5].

Because of this, alternative relaxation processes, initiated to relieve the internal stress, play a key role in determining the overall behaviour of the composite [6, 7]. At room temperature the most important alternative processes are likely to be plastic flow in the matrix and damage accumulation. Damage accumulation in MMCs can occur either by cracking of the hard second phase reinforcement [8-10] or by debonding along the reinforcement-matrix interface [11]. The degree to which damage accumulation or plastic flow occur depends on the level of stress experienced by the second phase reinforcement. This depends on the flow strength supported by the matrix. Soft matrices are less likely to generate the high degrees of stress concentration necessary to create interface debonding or to nucleate brittle failure in the reinforcements. Both plastic relaxation and damage accumulation occur simultaneously, and can be initiated at very low strains [7]. Moreover, both processes depend on the strength of the matrix, which can be varied by cold-working, temperature and heat treatments.

Damage accumulation and plastic flow in MMCs can be studied by classical mechanical tests, such as tensile, compressive, hardness, creep or rupture mechanics tests. These techniques provide direct information on the mechanical properties of the material, like yield stress, tensile strength, toughness, ductility, but they are destructive by nature and the microstructure is strongly altered by the test.

The anelastic behaviour of crystalline solids is primarily caused by the motion of structural defects around their equilibrium position. To induce such a motion, applied stresses smaller than in classical mechanical tests are needed, which has the consequence that the microstructure is not strongly modified. Anelasticity is an interesting property which is at the basis of nondestructive internal friction techniques for studying the structural defects of

crystalline materials [12]. Internal friction measurement is a technique very sensitive to the mobility of the structural defects, such as dislocation, and is then well suited for studying the mechanisms of microplastic deformation [13, 14]. Furthermore, it has been proved to be sensitive to the formation of fatigue cracks in stainless steel [15]. Therefore, internal friction seems to be a suitable technique to study relaxation phenomena produced in MMCs by internal stress around reinforcements. It should also allow to identify the relaxation phenomena, plastic flow or damage accumulation, which take place at metal-fiber interfaces, by considering the different features of IF spectra [16].

The aim of this work is, above all, to check whether internal friction is sensitive to interface loosening in MMCs. Thus, IF measurements as a function of the vibration amplitude have been performed, in order to detect the loss of mechanical properties of metal-ceramic interfaces.

EXPERIMENTS

Al-4wt%Cu based composite samples containing 10%, 20%, and 30% volumetric fraction of alumina fibers (Saffil) were produced by the method of squeeze-casting [17] at Alusuisse-Lonza Services Ltd., Neuhausen, Switzerland. Unreinforced Al-4wt%Cu samples were produced simultaneously with the composites in the same solidification process. Fig. 5 shows the microstructure of the produced composites, photographed in a confocal microscope. The distribution of the fibers in the AlCu matrix is clearly shown.

Rod shaped specimens, 2 mm diameter and 40 mm in effective length were obtained by machining. After being solution treated at 535 °C for 2 h, the specimens were quenched in water. In this way, Cu was retained in supersaturated solid solution (SSS) and the initial state for internal friction measurements was well defined and reproducible. Afterwards, the specimens were mounted in an inverted torsion pendulum [18]. IF was measured automatically, by the method of the free decay of the oscillations, at a frequency of about 1 Hz.

Damping (IF) and frequency (f) were measured as a function of the maximum shear strain amplitude ϵ (between $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $8 \cdot 10^{-3}$) at constant temperature (T), in order to study the mechanism of internal stress relaxation in the composites. IF measurements were always taken increasing the vibration amplitude. IF was calculated in two different ways. The first method consists in taking a portion of the signal representing the free decay of vibrations and analysing it in terms of the Fourier transform to obtain the internal friction and the frequency [19]. This method has the advantage to reduce the effect of interference vibrations, but do not allow to detect high amplitude phenomena, since the signal must be averaged over several vibration periods. The second method (IF bis) consists in using the classical relation:

$$IF = 1/(n \pi) * \ln (\epsilon_1 / \epsilon_n) \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_1 is the maximum vibration amplitude reached during the excitation and ϵ_n is the amplitude measured n periods later. The chosen value for n was always 3, in order to have IF values at the highest vibration amplitude. Actually, IF can exhibit non linear behaviour at high amplitude. Here the interest was focused on the high amplitude regime. IF was measured also as a function of time at constant maximum shear strain amplitudes around $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$, in order to study the effect of mechanical fatigue. The resolution of IF measurements is about $0.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

The shear modulus (G) was determined from the vibration frequency f , using the relation:

$$G = (8\pi LIf^2)/r^4 \quad (2)$$

where L and r are the sample's length and radius respectively, and I is the pendulum momentum of inertia.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the evolution of internal friction (IF) and shear elastic modulus (G) at room temperature as a function of the vibration amplitude in the range 10^{-5} - 10^{-3} for the composite AlCu-20%Saffil in the as quenched state. At the lowest vibration amplitudes IF is almost constant. Then IF exhibits a sharp step, indicated by an arrow in the figure, in the 10^{-3} amplitude range. At higher vibration amplitudes IF begins to grow rapidly. The IF step in the 10^{-3} range corresponds to a singularity in the modulus curve. This singularity, the step in the damping spectrum, and the existence of two different damping regimes before and after the step point out that a dissipative mechanism has been activated in the composite in the 10^{-3} amplitude range.

Fig. 1: Internal friction (IF) and shear elastic modulus (G) as a function of vibration amplitude for AlCu-20%Saffil in the as quenched state.

Since this mechanism operates at high amplitudes, we have focused our attention on high amplitude damping, and we have tried to observe this phenomenon better with a second method to calculate internal friction, which could be more sensitive to high amplitude effects (IF bis). Fig. 2 shows the comparison between IF measured by the Fourier transform and IF bis, calculated with the relation (1) during the first three vibration periods after excitation. The measured specimen is identical to that analysed in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2: Comparison between IF measured with the Fourier transform and IF bis for a AlCu-20%Saffil composite.

Just as the sample in Fig. 1, the composite specimen exhibits a step in its IF spectrum at an amplitude around $3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$. If we consider the behaviour of IF bis, we find that, at low amplitudes, it is not very different from that of IF calculated by the Fourier transform, but, in correspondence with the IF step, a sharp damping peak is exhibited by the IF bis spectrum. At higher amplitudes IF bis takes higher values compared to IF measured with the Fourier transform. It is evident from these observations that IF bis can be a more sensitive tool compared to IF calculated with the Fourier transform to follow high amplitude phenomena in MMCs. In fact, the dissipative mechanism activated in the composite in the 10^{-3} range is better resolved in IF bis spectra and results distinctly in a peak. Moreover, IF bis spectra reveal a high damping background at high amplitudes, which was hidden in IF spectra calculated with the Fourier transform.

In order to understand the nature of the dissipative mechanism originating the peak in Fig. 2, an AlCu-20%Saffil specimen and the corresponding unreinforced alloy have been compared. Fig. 3 shows the evolution of internal friction (IF bis) and shear elastic modulus (G) at room temperature as a function of the vibration amplitude for the composite and the corresponding unreinforced alloy, both in the as quenched state. IF behaviour is very different in the two cases. The composite exhibits the sharp IF peak P at a strain amplitude around $4 \cdot 10^{-3}$, while the unreinforced alloy exhibits only an IF background. Therefore, the dissipative phenomenon responsible for the peak P is active only in the composite.

Fig. 3 shows also that the shear elastic modulus of the composite (29 GPa) is higher than the one of the corresponding unreinforced alloy (25 GPa), and that it slightly decreases as a function of strain amplitude.

Fig. 3: Internal friction (IF bis) and shear elastic modulus (G) as a function of vibration amplitude for AlCu-20%Saffil and the corresponding unreinforced alloy, both in the as quenched state.

The shape of the peak P, exhibited by the composite, is amazingly similar to the amplitude-dependent damping behaviour of a localized solid friction device [18]. In Fig. 4 it is shown the model of a localized solid friction device and its anelastic response. The resemblance of the amplitude-dependent damping behaviour of the composite and the rheological model in Fig. 4 shows that a phenomenon of solid friction is active in the composite. This phenomenon is activated at a critical strain around $3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (Fig. 2), and is localized, i.e. a breakaway phenomenon.

While taking IF measurements as a function of the amplitude, the fracture of the composite occurred at amplitudes around $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Since this strain value is very low, and in cold-working experiments strains up to 4% were applied without the occurrence of any fracture, mechanical fatigue during IF measurements is responsible for this cracking. Mechanical fatigue fracture occurs in the composite at a strain not much higher than the critical strain for the peak P. Furthermore, no fatigue fracture and no peak P were exhibited by the unreinforced alloy. These

facts suggest that the breakaway mechanism connected with P is the formation and propagation of cracks in the composite. These are likely to rise at metal-fiber interfaces, where the stress concentration is higher.

Fig. 4: Model of a localized solid friction device (a) and its amplitude-dependent damping behaviour (b). J and K are the elastic constants of two springs, ϵ_{el} and ϵ_{an} the elastic and anelastic strain respectively, σ_{ocr} the critical stress at which a sliding block begins to move, σ_0 the amplitude of the applied cyclic stress, Δ the relaxation intensity.

a) after quenching

b) after cycling in the IF pendulum

Fig. 5: AlCu-20%Saffil microstructure in the as quenched state (a) and after mechanical cycling in the internal friction pendulum (b).

Fig. 5 shows the microstructure of an AlCu-20%Saffil specimen just after quench (a) and after the mechanical cycling during IF measurements (b). The specimen has been cycled up to the fracture. The region shown in Fig. 5 (b) has been taken far away from the fracture surface and at the periphery of the cylindrical specimen, where the applied torsional stress is higher. After quenching, small cracks are detectable (see the arrow in Fig. 5 (a)), which rise at metal-fiber interfaces and propagate into the metal matrix. These cracks are likely to be produced by the high thermal stresses generated in the composite during the quenching process or during cooling from the infiltration temperature in the production stage. After cycling, crack density has increased and cracks become larger (see the arrow in Fig. 5 (b)). They propagate deeply into the metal matrix and create bridges between the fibers. Fig. 5 proves that the formation and propagation of cracks in the composite while taking IF spectra as a function of the amplitude is effective, and that this phenomenon could be the origin of the damping peak in Fig. 2.

As a conclusion, the internal friction peak P seems to be related to damage accumulation and to matrix-fiber debonding produced in the composite by mechanical stress. Internal friction can "feel" the development of cracks at metal-fiber interfaces in MMCs at the very initial stage, non destructively, and averaging over a large amount of material. It can be advantageously used to characterize the quality of interfaces in MMCs.

Fig. 6: IF and G as a function of the number of cycles in AlCu-20%Saffil (as quenched state). The vibration amplitude is $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and the temperature 300 K.

To check the effectiveness of the relation between fatigue cracks growth and IF behaviour in the composite, IF measurements as a function of time at constant strain amplitude were performed. Fig. 6 shows IF and G in AlCu-20%Saffil (as quenched state) as a function of the number of cycles at a vibration amplitude of $6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and at room temperature. To activate damage accumulation, the applied strain was chosen higher than the critical strain for P occurrence. After about 90000 cycles the fracture of the specimen occurred.

Fig. 7: Internal friction (IF bis) as a function of the applied stress for three AlCu based composites reinforced with 10%, 20% and 30% Saffil, each in the as quenched state.

The damage accumulation produced in the composite by mechanical fatigue comes with a decrease in the elastic modulus and an increase in internal friction (Fig. 6). These two parameters can be advantageously used to follow damage accumulation in MMCs subjected to mechanical fatigue.

We have tried to characterize the strength of metal-fiber interfaces in different composites by means of the solid friction peak P. This peak is connected with the formation and development of cracks at metal-fiber interfaces and, thus, should allow to detect the limit at which different composites undergo damage accumulation and crack development at interfaces.

Fig. 7 shows the damping spectra (IF bis) as a function of the applied stress for the three composites AlCu-10%Saffil, AlCu-20%Saffil and AlCu-30%Saffil, which have the same metal matrix, but different reinforcement volume fractions. The applied stress corresponds to the torsional stress which must be exerted on the specimen during the excitation stage to reach ϵ_1 , the desired maximum vibration amplitude. It is evident from Fig. 7 that all the composites exhibit the solid friction P, but at a stress which becomes higher increasing the fiber content. It can be concluded that a higher reinforcement fraction leads to metal-fiber interfaces where the stress concentration is lower. As a consequence, damage accumulation and crack development in the MMCs can be shifted at higher stresses by increasing the reinforcement content.

CONCLUSIONS

Al-4%Cu based MMCs reinforced with 10%, 20% and 30% Al₂O₃ (Saffil) fibers have been characterized by internal friction measurements. In internal friction measurements as a function of the vibration amplitude a solid friction peak has been found, which is connected with the loss of mechanical properties of metal-ceramic interfaces.

On this basis, IF measurements allowed us to characterize in different composites damage accumulation, the formation and propagation of cracks at matrix-fiber interfaces, and also the strength of these interfaces.

Furthermore, internal friction measurements have allowed to follow damage accumulation consequent to mechanical fatigue in the composite. The elastic modulus of the composite is confirmed to have better performances than the one of the unreinforced alloy.

REFERENCES

1. L. Parrini, R. Schaller, *Scripta metall.* **28** (6), 763 (1993).
2. K. K. Chawla, *Composites Materials*, New York, Springer-Verlag (1987).
3. P. Withers, W. Stobbs, O. Pedersen, *Acta metall.* **37**, 3061 (1989).
4. M. Taya, K. Lulay, D. Lloyd, *Acta metall.* **39**, 73 (1991).
5. A. Levy, M. Papazian, *Acta metall.* **39**, 2255 (1991).
6. A. Allen et al., *Acta metall.* **40**, 2361 (1992).
7. P. Withers, T. Lorentzen, O. Pedersen, in *Proc. 12th Riso Int. Symp.*, ed. N. Hansen et al., Riso National Laboratory, Denmark, 189 (1991).
8. A. Vasudevan et al., *Mater. Sci. Engng A* **107**, 63 (1989).
9. W. Hunt, J. Brockenbrough, P. Magnusen, *Scripta metall.* **25**, 15 (1991).
10. D. Lloyd, *Acta metall.* **39**, 59 (1991).
11. Z. Wang, R. Zhang, *Acta metall.* **42**, 1433 (1994).
12. W. Benoit, G. Gremaud, R. Schaller, *Anelasticity and dislocation Damping in: "Plastic Deformation of Amorphous and Semi-Crystalline Materials"*, ed. B. Escaig and G. G'sell, Les Edition de Physique, Paris (1982).
13. A. Munier, M. Maamouri, R. Schaller, *J. Nucl. Mat.* **202**, 54 (1993).
14. R. Schaller, J. Amman, P. Millet, *"Nondestructive Characterization of Materials II"*, ed. J. Bussiere et al., 345 (1987).
15. S. McGuire et al., *J. Mater. Res.* **8**, 2216 (1993).
16. L. Parrini, R. Schaller, *High Performance Composites*, ed. K. Chawla, P. Liaw, S. Fishman, TMS, Rosemont, 239 (1994).
17. G. Cappleman, J. Watts and T. Clyne, *J. Mat. Science* **20**, 2159 (1985).
18. A. Nowick and B. Berry, *Anelastic Relaxation in Crystalline Solids*, New York, Academic Press, 583 (1972).
19. Yoshida I. et al., *J. Phys. E: Sci. Instrum.* **14**, 1201 (1981).

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